

MATERIAL, PROCESS, STRUCTURE: MEETING THE CHALLENGE FOR A380, A350XWB AND BEYOND

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SUMMARY

This presentation explores the development of structural solutions that led to the A380. It goes on to describe how the latest technologies are being applied to ensure that the A350XWB meets even tougher objectives for performance, cost and environmental impact, and to set the agenda for the development of the next generation of passenger aircraft.